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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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DEVELOPING STUDENTS' SPEECH SKILLS BASED ON MULTIMODAL APPROACH IN ENGLISH TEACHING

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Abstract: This article analyzes the methods and techniques for improving students' speech skills based on the multimodal approach to teaching English. The simultaneous delivery of information through several sensory channels, known as multimodal instruction, is considered an effective means of developing students' speaking, writing, listening, and reading skills. With a particular emphasis on the influence of audiovisual elements on listening comprehension, the paper presents a theoretical overview of the linguistic and psycho-pedagogical foundations of multimodal teaching. In addition, it offers methodological strategies for the use of instructional films in the classroom, supported by international best practices and practical recommendations.

Key words: multimodal literacy, multimodal approach, visual-semantic perception, visual, auditory, textual, kinesthetic channels, visual literacy.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini o'qitishda multimodal yondashuv asosida talabalarning nutqiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish usullari va texnikalari tahlil etiladi. Bir vaqtning o'zida bir nechta sezgi kanallari orqali ma'lumotni qabul qilishga asoslangan multimodal ta'lim yondashuvi talabalar nutq, yozuv, tinglab tushunish va o'qish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishning samarali vositasi sifatida ko'riladi. Maqolada multimodal o'qitishning lingvistik va psixo-pedagogik asoslari nazariy jihatdan yoritilib, ayniqsa audiovizual elementlarning tinglab tushunish jarayoniga ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, xorijiy ilg'or tajriba asosida o'quv jarayonida ta'limiy filmlardan foydalanish bo'yicha metodik strategiyalar va amaliy tavsiyalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: multimodal savodxonlik, multimodal yondashuv, vizual-semantik idrok, vizual, audial, matnli, kinestetik kanallar, vizual savodxonlik.

Аннотация: В статье анализируются методы и приёмы совершенствования речевых навыков студентов, основанные на мультимодальном подходе к обучению английскому языку. Мультимодальное обучение, при котором информация воспринимается одновременно через несколько сенсорных каналов, считается эффективным средством развития навыков говорения, письма, аудирования и чтения. Особое внимание уделяется влиянию аудиовизуальных элементов на понимание устной речи, представлены теоретические основы лингвистического и психолого-педагогического характера мультимодального обучения. Кроме того, даны методические рекомендации по использованию учебных фильмов на занятиях, основанные на международном опыте и практических предложениях.

Ключевые слова: мультимодальная грамотность, мультимодальный подход, визуально-семантическое восприятие, визуальный, аудиальный, текстовый, кинестетический каналы, визуальная грамотность.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of international communication and globalization, improving the effectiveness of English language teaching is one of the urgent issues. The quality of education is inextricably linked with the introduction of modern pedagogical technologies. In recent years, teaching using information and communication technologies and multimedia has been widely applied in teaching foreign languages. Researchers note that information technologies have become an indispensable tool for increasing students' interest in lessons and developing visual-semantic perception, which allows the activation of students' cognitive, intellectual, and independent activities.

The aim is to develop a methodology for improving students' speech skills based on a multimodal approach to teaching English. A multimodal approach is understood as conveying information simultaneously through different modal means – text, speech (audio), image, movement, etc. Such integrated education influences students' various sensory channels and serves to thoroughly assimilate knowledge. In particular, educational

videos, due to the simultaneous transmission of information through the organs of hearing and vision, leave a stronger cognitive imprint on the student. As a result, the student's attention is attracted, listening comprehension is facilitated, and memorization is enhanced.

Multimodal education is effective not only in imparting knowledge but also in developing skills and competencies, and it is especially important in subjects that require understanding oral speech, such as a foreign language. The term multimodal in pedagogy means that information is presented simultaneously in several ways – for example, through visual, auditory, textual, and even kinesthetic channels. Research shows that each student has a unique way of receiving and assimilating information: some are more inclined to learn by listening, while others understand better through visual demonstrations.

A multimodal approach, therefore, provides educational material in multiple forms, meeting the needs of different students and ensuring that each of them succeeds in a way that suits them. For example, an educational video may contain elements such as simultaneous speech (audio), images, texts, and music – all of which together improve the student's understanding and memory of new material.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to research by psychologists and educational scientists, the human brain can use several channels at the same time when processing information. In this case, the depth of understanding increases when information is presented in different forms. According to R. Mayer's theory of multimedia education, the combined presentation of educational material in visual and audio formats leads to the formation of two different codes in the student's mind – that is, pictorial and verbal information – which improves the perception and consolidation of knowledge in memory ^[5]. In other words, the combination of audio and video helps the student simultaneously receive information from two different sources and, by connecting them, understand the logical content. Furthermore, information that may be missing in one modal channel is supplemented by another modal channel – for example, in a video, this meaning is revealed through context or images. This significantly facilitates contextual understanding in learning a foreign language.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The use of educational videos is one of the practical tools for implementing a multimodal approach. Through video materials, students learn not only by listening but also by watching – that is, they perceive oral speech in a form close to natural face-to-face communication. Factors such as facial expressions and gestures of the characters in the video, the environment, and the visual context help to understand the content of the speech being listened to. This is important from a linguistic point of view because, in real communicative situations, meaning is understood not only from words but also from nonverbal cues and context. Thus, learning through video allows students to master the language in a “live” state, along with all aspects of communication.

In addition, educational videos also have a positive effect on the psychological state of students. First, video lessons are usually more interesting and interactive, which attracts students' attention and arouses interest in learning. In particular, watching videos in the classroom can be more enjoyable for students than listening to traditional text or audio, which increases their motivation to learn. In his study, researcher H. Mirvan found that using videos in the classroom significantly increases students' motivation and participation in the lesson – because videos enrich the lesson content through real-life situations and provide students with a lively and interesting context. The natural and meaningful context created by videos increases students' interest in learning the language and makes the lesson more meaningful ^[1].

At the same time, a study by K. Woottipong also found that students who took lessons using video materials had higher interest and more positive attitudes towards learning English than those who took lessons using traditional methods ^[2]. Therefore, video lessons encourage students to actively participate in the lesson, express their opinions, and thereby develop their communicative competence.

The above theoretical considerations show that the use of a multimodal approach creates a linguistically richer environment in foreign language learning and increases students' positive attitudes and motivation to study from a psycho-pedagogical point of view. Furthermore, working with multimodal materials creates a basis for the more complex formation of students' auditory comprehension skills – because in this case, the listener perceives not only sound but also images, processing information through different areas of the brain.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The methodology for developing students' speech skills based on a multimodal approach is widely used in various education systems around the world, and many studies have provided evidence of its positive effect. In particular, the results of foreign scientific research confirm that the listening comprehension skills and motivation of students who receive education with a multimodal approach develop better than those who use

traditional methods. Thus, a multimodal approach not only improves learning outcomes but also turns the educational process into a morally stimulating factor for students. At the same time, in a number of international developments in foreign language teaching methodologies, there are also successful experiences in expanding students' vocabulary, improving pronunciation, and instilling cultural knowledge using multimedia tools, including video lessons ^[3].

From a psycho-pedagogical point of view, multimodal education increases students' activity in the lesson and also forms their independent learning skills. Since video lessons usually arouse interest in students, they tend to independently search for additional videos or materials on the same topic on the Internet after the lesson. This strengthens their search and independent learning skills. It is known from advanced foreign experience that in countries such as the USA, Great Britain, and Canada, online video lesson platforms are widely used in teaching a foreign language – for example, Khan Academy Kids, BBC Learning English, British Council video materials, etc. These platforms contain short and interactive video lessons designed for students of different levels, and it is emphasized that they are highly effective in learning.

Importantly, the effectiveness of the multimodal approach increases not only the student's listening skills but also their overall motivation and self-confidence. As a result of working with video materials, students feel satisfied with their ability to understand what they have heard, which motivates them for further studies. Some researchers (for example, W.H. Hsu) have noted that when short video lessons are regularly used, students' interest in learning English is stabilized and even motivates them to strive for higher results ^[4]. In conclusion, it is worth noting that the use of educational videos based on a multimodal approach in teaching English is an effective strategy that meets the requirements and proposals of modern pedagogy. This approach is especially useful for students of higher education, since they have already formed independent thinking and are more prepared for interactive learning. Multimodal education can focus students' attention on one point, simultaneously impart knowledge through different emotions, and turn the lesson into a lively dialogue and experience.

The theoretical analyses and practical examples presented in the article show that the formation of students' language skills using a multimodal approach, while linguistically allowing students to perceive the language in a real context, increases their learning motivation and enhances their involvement in the lesson in psycho-pedagogical terms. Through video lessons, students' interest and enthusiasm for a foreign language increase, and they strive to demonstrate their knowledge more actively. This, in turn, has a positive effect on their overall academic results. In order to widely introduce this strategy into educational practice, it is necessary to improve the skills of teachers and train them in the use of multimedia. It would also be useful to form a bank of educational videos developed in accordance with textbooks and methodological guides. When these conditions are met, the use of a multimodal approach can be effective not only in teaching English but also in other subjects.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, the strategy of using educational videos based on a multimodal approach is a suitable and effective method for today's information-age students, which enriches the learning process, forms important skills such as listening comprehension, and takes the quality of English teaching to a new level. By implementing this approach in practice, we not only teach students the language but also form in them the skills of the 21st century – working with multimedia, visual literacy, and independent reading and learning.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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